

PHOSPHATE AND AMMONIUM RECOVERY IN A THREE CHAMBERED MICROBIAL ELECTROLYSIS CELL

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An alternative to traditional livestock manure management is the implementation of circular agrosystems approaches. The recovery of phosphate, among other nutrients, helps closing natural cycles and take a step forward within the framework of closed-loop agriculture. In addition to more conventional nutrient recovery technologies, bioelectrochemical systems (BES) are emerging as candidates for the recovery of multiple resources from waste. BES are devices where exoelectrogenic microorganisms catalyse oxidation and/or reduction reactions in an electrode (anode and/or cathode, respectively) and, in combination with cation or anion exchange membranes, allow the recovery of nutrients [1]. In this work, a lab-scale three-chambered microbial electrolysis cell (MEC) has been operated in continuous mode for the recovery of phosphate together with ammonia from digested pig slurry, to obtain a concentrated nutrient solution as a potential source of fertilizer in the form of struvite [2]. Struvite is a salt composed of ammonia, phosphate, and magnesium (heptahydrate), and has been described as a slow-release fertilizer. The MEC was composed of an anode and a cathode compartments, separated by a recovery compartment delimited with a cation exchange membrane on the anode side and an anion exchange membrane on the cathode side. The digestate was first fed to the anode compartment to recover the ammonium, and then the anodic effluent was circulated to feed the cathode compartment and to recover the phosphate. In some of the assays, the digestate was acidified with H_2SO_4 to favour phosphate solubilization. The maximum average removal efficiencies for phosphate and ammonium were $36\% \pm 0\%$ and $20\% \pm 4\%$, respectively. Salt precipitation was avoided in the reactor due to the pH of the recovered solution (<7). An increase of pH value to 8 outside the reactor would be enough to recover most of the potential struvite ($0.21 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$), while the addition of up to 0.2 mM of magnesium to the nutrient recovered solution would enhance struvite production from 5.6 to 17.7 mM, according to Visual MINTEQ software modelling. Phosphate solubilization is revealed as a key issue in the recovery of struvite from livestock manure in BES, as acidification

with H_2SO_4 can interfere, on the one hand, with the growth of biomass in the anode compartment, and, on the other hand, with phosphate migration. Phosphate solubilization techniques compatible with BES performance should be evaluated to improve system recovery efficiency. However, the application of three-chambered MECs for nutrient recovery from high-concentration wastewater is a promising technology to avoid phosphate mineral extraction or ammonia production through industrial processes while closing natural nutrient cycles.

Acknowledgements.

This research was funded by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (RTA2015-00079-C02-01 and PID2020-118830RR-I0). The support of the CERCA Program and of the Consolidated Research Group of Sustainability in Biosystems (ref. 2021 SGR 01568), both from the Generalitat de Catalunya, is also acknowledged.

References

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